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Corrosion performance of laser-wire-directed energy deposited austenitic stainless steel claddings in marine environments

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Abstract

Stainless steel claddings are an advantageous coating method for marine structures because of their strong metallurgical bond and corrosion resistance in saline environments. In this work, we evaluate the corrosion performance of 309L stainless steel claddings on carbon steel fabricated using a laser-wire-directed energy deposition additive manufacturing method by exposing samples to a 35 °C 5 wt.% NaCl salt spray environment and comparing their corroded surfaces and mass loss to wrought 304 stainless steel and carbon steel. The 35 °C temperature and higher chloride concentration accelerate corrosion rates in this study compared to prior room temperature immersion test data. The stainless steel claddings have outstanding resistance to the salt spray environment, with a 56 % lower corrosion rate compared to the 304 SS and a 99.8 % lower corrosion rate compared to the carbon steel, showing their potential benefit for a cost effective corrosion protection method for marine structures.

Keywords: metallic coatings; cladding; stainless steel; salt spray; directed energy deposition

1. Introduction

Carbon steels are the most widely used structural metals because of their suitable mechanical properties, weldability, and low cost; however, they readily corrode in marine environments. Stainless steels (SS) are often utilized in their place when there are prolonged corrosion concerns, though the additions of Cr and Ni make SS alloys many times more expensive than carbon steels and cost prohibitive for large components. Therefore, coatings are desirable for protecting carbon steel components used in marine energy applications and SS overlay claddings are a choice coating method because of their strong metallurgical bond to the carbon steel substrate [1], [2], [3]. During cladding, SS feedstock, either wire or powder, is repeatedly melted by a heat source over the carbon steel substrate, which then metallurgically bonds the dissimilar metals, forming a strong and corrosion resistant composite. Cladding processes that use a high energy heat source (e.g., laser, electron beam) rather than a plasma arc are desirable for creating claddings with minimal distortion, a small heat-affected zone, and thin layer(s) [4], [5], [6]. In particular, laser-wire-directed energy deposition (DED), an additive manufacturing (3D printing) -based process is an ideal cladding fabrication technique because it uses spooled welding wire, which has substantially lower cost compared to powder [4], [6], [7].

In this work, we fabricate austenitic 309L SS claddings on low carbon steel substrates using laser-wire-DED and examine their corrosion behavior in a 35 °C 5 wt.% NaCl salt spray environment following ASTM B117 [8]. Corroded surfaces are optically imaged and corrosion rate is calculated following ASTM G1 [9]. The claddings' corrosion behavior is compared to wrought 304 SS and low carbon steel, as well as prior immersion experiments in room temperature 3.5 wt.% NaCl [10] to benchmark the corrosion rates measured in this work.

2. Methodology

2.1. Cladding fabrication

Claddings were fabricated using 0.889 mm diameter ER309L SS welding wire and 1018 carbon steel substrates with dimensions of 127 mm x 127 mm x 25.4 mm. The chemical compositions of the starting materials were measured using inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry, combustion, and inert gas fusion according to ASTM E1019 [11] and are listed in Table 1. Alloy 309L is typically used as the buttering (first) layer when cladding on carbon and low alloy steels [12], [13], as it is over-alloyed (24 wt.% Cr, 13 wt.% Ni) to compensate for dilution with the base metal. Therefore, a 309L SS cladding on carbon steel with 25% dilution has a composition similar to that of 304 SS (18Cr-8Ni).

Table 1: Starting material compositions (wt.%)

Alloy	Fe	Cr	Ni	Mn	Si	C ¹	N ²	O ³	P	S ¹	Co	Cu	Mo
309L SS wire	Bal.	23.30	12.62	1.75	0.33	0.01	0.13	0.008	0.025	0.006	0.18	0.08	0.07
1018 carbon steel substrate	Bal.	0.12	0.01	0.77	0.27	0.15	0.008	0.003	0.015	0.025	0.01	-	0.08

¹ Determined by combustion-infrared absorbance (C, S)

² Determined by inert gas fusion – thermal conductivity (N)

³ Determined by inert gas fusion – absorbance (O)

A Meltio M450 laser-wire-DED system was used to fabricate the claddings in this study. Spooled wire is vertically fed by an extruder, where it is melted by six independent diode lasers positioned 60 ° apart, which converge on a single 2.5 mm focal point and operate at a uniform power during cladding, as shown in Figure 1 (a). The lasers completely melt the ER309L SS and the top of the carbon steel substrate, creating a strong metallurgical bond upon solidification. Argon was used as a chamber and cover gas during cladding. Claddings were fabricated in a two-layer strategy using 800 W laser power, 600 mm/min travel speed, and 450 mm/min wire feed rate, which were optimized in previous research [6], [14]. The two-layer claddings are approximately 1 to 1.2 mm thick.

Figure 1: Illustration of the laser-wire-DED cladding process, (b) Cross section view of an as-fabricated cladding after surface grinding, showing various microstructural regions

2.2. Corrosion testing

Specimens were surface ground and sectioned to 15 mm x 10 mm x 0.5 mm using a wire-electrical discharge machine and subsequently ground using 240 to 400 grit SiC paper to remove the as-cast layer. Since the claddings are relatively thin, the top 0.5 mm of the cladding was sampled to be away from the carbon steel base metal, as shown in Figure 1 (b). The cladding samples were benchmarked using 1018 carbon steel cut from the substrate material and 304 SS (18Cr-8Ni) as a wrought comparison; these samples were cut and ground similarly. All samples were ultrasonicated in isopropyl alcohol prior to exposure.

Salt spray testing was performed using a Q-fog model 600 chamber following ASTM B117 [8]. Before and after exposure, samples were weighed using a Sartorius ME36S microbalance to measure their mass for calculating corrosion rate. Specimens were exposed to a continuous salt spray fog at 35 °C for 0.125, 1, 3, 10, and 30 days to examine their time-dependent corrosion behavior. The samples were positioned 20° from vertical in the chamber [8] in custom plastic sample holders, and three specimens were exposed per alloy / time combination. Immediately after removing from the chamber, the samples were dried to remove moisture. Corroded surfaces were imaged using an optical microscope. The samples were then cleaned and weighed multiple times after exposure to remove corrosion products without removal of base material. The first cleaning and weighing step included ultrasonication in DI water for 60 s, then isopropyl alcohol for 300 s, followed by weighing, but it was clear that this cleaning step did not remove all visible corrosion products from the carbon steel samples, which were heavily corroded. The second and third rounds of cleaning were performed by lightly scrubbing the corrosion products using a non-scratch sponge, followed by ultrasonication in isopropyl alcohol for 300 s and weighing, which was effective.

Corrosion rate (CR) was calculated following ASTM G1 [9] using:

$$CR \{\mu\text{m}/\text{yr}\} = (K \times W) / (A \times t \times \rho) \quad (1)$$

where K is a unit conversion constant ($8.76 \times 10^7 \mu\text{m}/\text{yr}$), W is the mass loss in g, A is the sample area in cm^2 , t is the exposure time in hr, and ρ is the material's density in g/cm^3 .

3. Results

Figure 2 shows the corroded surfaces after 3 hr, 3 days, and 30 days. The carbon steel specimens form heavy corrosion products after 3 hr. After 3 days, the corrosion products appear thick and uneven, completely covering the samples; both red and black oxides are observed in the 30 day samples. The 304 SS contains smaller ($< 100 \mu\text{m}$) pits after 3 hr, and a red-yellow scale forms after 3 days. While corrosion products are evident on the 304 SS, they are visibly much thinner than the carbon steel. By comparison, the SS cladding sample does not show clear pitting until 3 days. After 30 days, only a few patches of light reddish corrosion products are observed, like in Figure 2 (i); in general, these were more common around the edges of the samples, but the SiC grinding marks are still visible after 30 days, indicating the surface was left mostly intact.

Figure 2: Optical images of corroded surfaces after exposure (a) - (c) Carbon steel, (d) - (f) 304 SS, and (g) - (i) SS cladding. (a), (d), and (g) 3 hr, (b), (e), (h) 3 days, and (c), (f), and (i) 30-day exposure

Figure 3 shows the CR for all sample types as a function of cleaning cycle and exposure time. For all sample types, the first cleaning's CR deviates from the second and third cleanings' because ultrasonication without scrubbing was ineffective at removing clinging corrosion products; this is especially noticeable in the 10-day carbon steel samples, where one specimen was measured to gain a large mass from its corrosion products not being removed. The 2nd and 3rd cleaning CRs more accurately represent the actual. Additionally, there is high error at the early exposure times because relatively high variation in mass loss (or gain) with relatively little corrosion product formation and removal. Therefore, the longer exposure times also more accurately represent the actual CRs, which agrees with previous studies by Montgomery et al. [15], [16]. However, the exception to this is the 30-day carbon steel samples – during the 2nd cleaning, the samples had corroded through-thickness in several locations and begun to disintegrate, so they could not be scrubbed vigorously enough to remove all visible corrosion products. Thus, the reported corrosion rates for the SS cladding and 304 SS samples are from the 30-day 3rd cleaning, while the carbon steel is from the 10-day 3rd cleaning, as listed in Table 2.

The CR measurements from the salt spray testing in this research and previous experiments in room temperature 3.5 wt.% NaCl immersion tests [10] are shown in Table 2. The carbon steel has the highest CR by over several orders of magnitude, while the 304 SS and SS cladding CRs are lower because of their alloying with chromium. The SS cladding performs remarkably better than the 304 SS, having a CR 56 % lower than that of the 304 SS and 99.8 % lower than the carbon steel. CR was measured in 3.5 wt.% NaCl immersion tests using linear polarization resistance [17], and shows similar trends between samples, where the salt spray CRs reported in the current work are approximately 8-10x higher than in the immersion test, which is due to the elevated temperature and chloride contents.

We attribute this outstanding corrosion performance to the claddings' high alloying (23 wt.% Cr) and formation of a protective chromium oxide layer. When selecting SS feedstock materials, we intentionally chose alloy 309L for this reason. While higher Cr and Ni contents would make a bulk SS part significantly more expensive, the small cladding thickness (1 to 1.2 mm) allows for customized alloys / properties to attain increased material performance at minimally raised costs; therefore, SS claddings are highly desirable for large components exposed to marine environments, for their corrosion resistance in each environment and lower cost compared to fabricating an entire component out of a stainless steel alloy.

Figure 3: Calculated corrosion rates for (a) Carbon steel, (b) 304 SS, (c) SS cladding

Table 2: Corrosion rate comparison [$\mu\text{m/yr}$]. 3.5 wt.% NaCl immersion corrosion rates were calculated using linear polarization resistance following ASTM G102 [17] in ref. [10]

Testing	NaCl concentration	Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Carbon steel	304 SS	SS cladding
Salt spray (this work)	5 wt.%	35	1051 ± 49	4.8 ± 0.8	2.1 ± 0.4
Immersion [10]	3.5 wt.%	20	126 ± 8	0.55 ± 0.11	0.22 ± 0.13
Ratio			8.34	8.73	9.55

4. Conclusions

Austenitic 309L stainless steel claddings on carbon steel were fabricated using a laser-wire-directed energy deposition additive manufacturing technique and exposed to a 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 5 wt.% NaCl salt spray environment for up to 30 days. The cladding corrosion rates were benchmarked by 304 stainless steel and low carbon steel and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The carbon steel corrodes heavily after only three hours. Large corrosion products cover sample surfaces after one day of exposure and completely penetrate the sample thickness after 30 days.
- Small pits can be seen on the 304 SS after three hours, which evolve into thicker corrosion products at longer exposure times.
- The SS cladding has the lowest corrosion rate (2.1 $\mu\text{m/yr}$), which is 56 % lower than that of the 304 SS (4.8 $\mu\text{m/yr}$) and 99.8 % lower than that of the carbon steel (1051 $\mu\text{m/yr}$). Thus, the SS claddings presented in this work are highly desirable for a low cost corrosion protection method for marine applications.

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References

- [1] N. Switzner and Z. Yu, "Austenitic stainless steel cladding interface microstructures evaluated for petrochemical applications," *Weld J*, vol. 98, no. 2, pp. 50S-61S, 2019, doi: 10.29391/2019.98.004.
- [2] I. Sattari-Far and M. Andersson, "Cladding Effects on Structural Integrity of Nuclear Components," p. 73, 2006.
- [3] S. C. Bozeman, L. Daut, B. K. Bay, O. B. Isgor, and J. D. Tucker, "Time-Dependent 600 °C Post-Weld Heat Treatment Response of Laser-Wire-Directed Energy Deposited Austenitic Stainless Steel Claddings on Carbon Steel," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, 2025, doi: 10.1007/s11661-025-07791-8.
- [4] B. Wahlmann, C. Körner, and M. Nunn, "Electron beam wire cladding of nickel alloys and stainless steel on a reactor pressure vessel steel," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 811, no. March, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2021.141082.
- [5] R. A. Rahman Rashid, S. Abaspour, S. Palanisamy, N. Matthews, and M. S. Dargusch, "Metallurgical and geometrical characterisation of the 316L stainless steel clad deposited on a mild steel substrate," *Surf Coat Technol*, vol. 327, pp. 174–184, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2017.08.013.
- [6] S. C. Bozeman, O. B. Isgor, and J. D. Tucker, "Effects of processing conditions on the solidification and heat-affected zone of 309L stainless steel claddings on carbon steel using wire-directed energy deposition," *Surf Coat Technol*, vol. 444, no. 128698, p. 11, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2022.128698.
- [7] W. Li *et al.*, "Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of 308L stainless steel coatings fabricated by laser hot wire cladding," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 824, no. April, p. 141825, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2021.141825.
- [8] ASTM International, *ASTM B117 - Practice for Operating Salt Spray (Fog) Apparatus*. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2018. doi: 10.1520/B0117-18.
- [9] ASTM International, "ASTM G1 - 03 (2017) Standard Practice for Preparing, Cleaning, and Evaluating Corrosion Test Specimens," 2017. doi: 10.1520/G0001-03R11.2.
- [10] S. C. Bozeman, J. D. Tucker, and O. B. Isgor, "Corrosion Resistance of 309L Stainless Steel Claddings on Carbon Steel Produced with Wire-Fed Directed Energy Deposition," *Corrosion*, vol. 79, no. 7, pp. 771–781, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5006/4268>.
- [11] ASTM International, "ASTM E1019-18: Standard Test Methods for Determination of Carbon, Sulfur, Nitrogen, and Oxygen in Steel and in Steel, Iron, Nickel, and Cobalt Alloys by Various Combustion and Fusion Techniques," 2018. doi: 10.1520/E1019-18.2.
- [12] G. F. Li and J. Congleton, "Stress corrosion cracking of a low alloy steel to stainless steel transition weld in PWR primary waters at 292°C," *Corros Sci*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 1005–1021, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0010-938X(99)00131-6.
- [13] L. Dong, C. Ma, Q. Peng, E. H. Han, and W. Ke, "Microstructure and stress corrosion cracking of a SA508-309L/308L-316L dissimilar metal weld joint in primary pressurized water reactor environment," *J Mater Sci Technol*, vol. 40, pp. 1–14, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jmst.2019.08.035.
- [14] S. C. Bozeman, O. B. Isgor, and J. D. Tucker, "Area-based composition predictions of materials fabricated using simultaneous wire-powder-directed energy deposition," *Additive Manufacturing Letters*, vol. 11, p. 100254, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.addlet.2024.100254.
- [15] E. L. Montgomery, L. Marina Calle, A. C. Jerome Curran, and M. R. Kolody, "Timescale Correlation between Marine Atmospheric Exposure and Accelerated Corrosion Testing," in *Corrosion 2011*, 2011, pp. 1–15.
- [16] E. L. Montgomery, L. M. Calle, J. C. Curran, and M. R. Kolody, "Timescale Correlation between Marine Atmospheric Exposure and Accelerated Corrosion Testing-Part 2," in *Corrosion*, 2012, pp. 1–17.
- [17] ASTM International, "ASTM G102 - 80 (2015) Standard Practice for Calculation of Corrosion Rates and Related Information from Electrochemical Measurements," *Astm*, vol. 89, no. Reapproved 2015, pp. 1–7, 2015, doi: 10.1520/G0102-89R15E01.2.

